

IMPROVING PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE AS AN INTEGRAL PART IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS.

Sakbaeva Vitaliya

Head of the Uzbek language and literature department
Termez institute of engineering and technology
sakbaevavitavladimirovna@gmail.com

Yarmatova Yulduz

Senior English teacher
Termez institute of engineering and technology
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Annotation

Innovations in education require continuous improvement of the set of pedagogical technologies, methods, methods and educational tools in the educational process. Currently, innovative pedagogical activity is one of the important components of the educational activity of educational institutions. It is the innovative activity that creates the basis for ensuring the competitiveness of education in organizations in the market of educational services, contributes to the personal growth of students, the formation of general and professional competences, the professional development of teachers, and creative research.

Key words: pragmatics, communicative competence, main purpose of language teaching, pragmatic awareness, meaning in context.

An innovative approach to teaching in the framework of competence-based technologies depends on the content of education, teaching methods and forms of quality control of education.

The historical roots of competency approach issues are reflected in the works of Eastern thinkers Abu Rayhan Beruniy, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abdullah Avlani. In our historical heritage, many opinions are expressed about the issues of the importance and importance of the ideas of orientation to competency knowledge in the development of society.

Pragmatic competence represents the ability to construct statements, combine them into meaning (discourse), knowledge, rules, the ability to use the statement for various communicative functions, the ability to construct statements in a foreign language in accordance with the characteristics of the interaction of communicators and the socio-cultural context. This competence is expressed in the ability to build a statement in accordance with communicative and pragmatic purpose. There are three principles on which pragmatic competence is built. The first of them is the meaning of the expressed thought

(thing, event, concept, event). The second principle is the interaction of the interlocutors with each other and the context with them, and the context itself is the third principle.

We define pragmatics as a central element of pragmatic competence. Pragmatics is the study of how language is used in communication, paying more attention to how it is said rather than what(s) is said. American philosopher Ch. Morris. The philosopher studied it as a component of semiotics along with semantics and syntax (Morris C., 1938) [163].

As mentioned above, in order to better understand pragmatics both as a science and as a result/consequence of pragmatic competence, it is good to study some rules and ideas of pragmatics. The theory of speech acts is one of the fundamental (most basic) theories of pragmatics. In linguistics and philosophy of language, speech act is a statement (spoken word, sentence, thought, expression) with a performative function in language and communication. Scientist J.L. Austin, according to Austin, speech acts can be analyzed at three levels (Austin J.L., 1962):

- locative act (act), that is, pronouncing a statement: a factual (implemented) statement that includes phonetic, factual and ritual actions in accordance with the oral-verbal, syntactic and semantic aspects of any statement and its self-evident meaning;
- illocutionary act (act): the pragmatic "illocutionary force" of the statement, that is, its intended meaning as an action expressed by a suitable word in the given/this socio-cultural context;
- perlocutionary act (act): the actual factual result (effect) of the spoken statement (thought, word, sentence), for example, to persuade/convince someone to do something or to understand something, whether or not it was planned in advance, to scare, enlighten, inspire or to force.

Therefore, knowing the pragmatic norms of a foreign language ensures obtaining the desired perlocutionary action from the interlocutor, that is, ensures effective communication.

Humans are social creatures, and when they speak, they are usually having conversations with others (monologues/speeches are an exception). English philosopher Paul Grice states that when people speak, they have a desire for cooperation (or cooperation). P. For Grice, every statement/opinion that speaks "cooperation" means a potential/probable interference (a potential face-threatening action/act) with the personal rights, autonomy, and desires of

another person (Grice, H.P., 1968, 1969, 1975, 1989). That is why interlocutors must express their statements/opinions in a certain way.

As we know classroom environments worldwide are commonly teacher-centered, structured to complete the syllabus with little time during lessons to facilitate the practice of language where learners are involved in comprehension and production of pragmatic meaning. And the opportunities to use the target language in situations that approach real-world conversation are limited. For this reason, I realized that it is important to start investigating the integration of pragmatic competence in foreign language teaching. Since the ultimate aim of learning languages is communication, it is important to conduct a study that contributes to facilitating this aim with the help of pragmatics. This aim seems even more indispensable in contexts where little emphasis is given to developing communicative competence, in particular ESP contexts.

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